

AN INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFECTS OF DIFFICULTIES IN COMPETITION ON SPORTSMANSHIP BEHAVIORS WITHIN THE SCOPE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS LESSON

MÜSABAKAYA KATILIM DURUMUNUN BEDEN EĞİTİMİ VE SPOR DERSİ KAPSAMINDAKİ SPORTMENLİK DAVRANIŞLARI ÜZERİNE ETKİSİNİN ARAŞTIRILMASI

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to investigate the effect of participation in the competition of children studying at secondary school level on sportsmanship behaviors within the scope of Physical Education and Sports course. The scores obtained by the students from the scales were evaluated in terms of gender, participation in the competition, class level and branch in the competition. A total of 174 students, 92 girls and 82 boys, between the ages of 10-15, studying at secondary school participated in the study. Of the 174 students who participated in the study, 86 participated in the competition and 88 were students who never participated in the competition. In this study it was researched using the "Physical Education Class Sportsmanship Behavior Scale" (BEDSS) developed by Koç (2013) in order to determine the sportsmanship behaviors of the students in the Physical Education and Sports lesson according to their participation in the competition. As a result, there was no statistically significant difference between the students who participated in the competition and the students who did not participate in the competition ($P>0.05$). When the gender variable is examined, a statistically significant difference has been reached between girls and boys in the direction of increase in the total scores of BEDSDÖ ($P<0.05$). In comparisons made on the basis of class, it was determined that there was a statistically significant difference and the group from which this difference originated was between 5th and 7th grades ($5>7$, $P<0.05$). As a result, it can be said that the sportsmanship levels of the students are determined by their personal characteristics rather than the ones who participated in the competition. In addition, our results showed that girls' having a kind, gentle and more fragile structure in terms of their upbringing in the family and their outlook on life in society may cause their sportsmanship levels to be better than boys.

Keywords: Competition Participation, Physical Education, Sports, Sportsmanship.

ÖZET

Araştırmada, ortaokul seviyesinde eğitim gören çocukların, müsabakaya katılım durumlarının Beden Eğitimi ve Spor dersi kapsamındaki sportmenlik davranışlarına yönelik etkisinin araştırılması amaçlanmıştır. Öğrenciler ölçeklerden aldıkları puan, cinsiyet, müsabakaya katılım durumları, sınıf düzeyi ve müsabakaya katılım branşları açısından değerlendirilmiştir. Çalışmaya ortaokulda eğitim alan 10-15 yaşları arasında 92 kız, 82 erkek toplam 174 öğrenci katılmıştır. Çalışmaya katılan 174 öğrencinin 86'sı müsabakaya katılmış 88'i ise hiç müsabakaya katılmamış öğrencilerden oluşmaktadır. Yapılan araştırmada öğrencilerin müsabakaya katılım durumlarına göre Beden Eğitimi ve Spor dersi sportmenlik davranışlarını belirlemek için Koç (2013) tarafından geliştirilen "Beden Eğitimi Dersi Sportmenlik Davranışı Ölçeği" (BEDSDÖ) kullanılarak araştırma yapılmıştır. Sonuç olarak müsabakaya katılım gösteren öğrenciler ile katılım göstermeyen öğrenciler arasında BEDSDÖ puanlaması yapılmış hesaplanan puanlar değerlendirildiğinde istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bir farka erişilememiştir ($P>0,05$). Cinsiyet değişkeni incelendiğinde BEDSDÖ toplam puanlarına bakıldığında, kız ve erkek öğrenciler arasında, kız çocuklarında artış yönünde istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bir farka erişilmiştir ($P<0,05$). Sınıf bazında yapılan karşılaştırmalarda istatistiksel olarak anlamlı fark olduğu ve bu farkın kaynaklandığı grubun 5 ve 7. sınıflar arasında olduğu saptanmıştır ($5>7$, $P<0,05$). Sonuç olarak öğrencilerinin sportmenlik düzeylerini, müsabakaya katılmış olanlarından ziyade, kişisel özelliklerinin belirlediği söylenebilir. Ayrıca sonuçlarımız, kız çocuklarının hem aile içinde yetiştirilme tarzları hem de toplumdaki hayata bakış ve düşünce tarzı açısından ince, nazik ve daha kırılabilir bir yapıya sahip olmalarının sportmenlik düzeylerinin, erkek çocuklarından daha iyi olmasına neden olabileceğini göstermiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Beden Eğitimi, Müsabakaya Katılım, Spor, Sportmenlik

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INTRODUCTION

The effect of sports on individuals begins in childhood. In this context, studies have been conducted to investigate the effects of sports on mental states such as communication skills, anxiety levels and self-efficacy levels of people (Colak S et al. 2016, Sivri et al. 2017).

In the spirit of sports, competition, struggle and the tournament in which these are exhibited are indispensable. The places where the spirit of sports and the culture of competition are conveyed to the students and where they first encounter competitions are the Physical Education and Sports (PES) classes in the schools where they get education.

Competition is the best area where students will see that they need to work hard to achieve success, allowing them to use the training they get in PES classes for physical, psychological and performance development.

According to Turkish Language Society (TLS), the meaning of competitor is contender, racer. In PES classes, students can be instilled with models of ethical behavior in sportsmanship in society and respect to the game, the opponent as well as success in the competition.

Sportsmanship, which expresses the adoption of a certain behavior and mentality while complying with the rules, is voluntarily avoiding all kinds of physical and psychological bad behavior to the athlete competing in the competition, competing in a fair manner, respecting the values of the opponent and protecting their rights. (Doğar and Yağmur, 2019).

According to Pehlivan (2004), the concept of fair-play (sportsmanship) was first accepted as the respect for human dignity and was adopted as a moral principle that ensures fair and honest play in all fields of sports. Sportsmanship, which finds its place in the concepts of sports, is actually accepted as a moral concept and the basic principle of education; while it includes positive behaviors such as respect for others, obeying the rules of the game, fairness, justice, fair play and ethical behavior; it also rejects behaviors that are impossible to be accepted by the society, such as cheating, lying, not following the rules and humiliating people, which we call negative. (Yapan, 2007).

It is thought that the reason for giving importance to sportsmanship behavior as much as competition in physical education classes is to aim for the growth of individuals who will create our future as individuals who prioritize human behaviors based on respect for human beings. The concept of sportsmanship can be taught in a planned, programmed and practical way with recreational sports activities in sports clubs, competitions and tournaments at schools (Ford, Jubenville, & Phillips, 2012).

It is thought that the environment where sportsmanship behavior can best be observed is the Physical Education and Sports class, which is the class where the child feels the most free, has a wide range of motion, and can take responsibility. Physical education and educational games not only contribute to the physical development of individuals, but also positively affect their social and spiritual development.

With the physical activities, educational games and various branches applied in physical education classes, features such as socialization, awareness of their abilities, respect for different ideas and people, communication, sharing, solidarity, obeying the leader, recognizing the rules, acting with the group and generating new ideas can be developed. (Karafil A. ve ark. 2017).

The fact that sportsmanship behavior can be observed more effectively and healthily in Physical Education and Sports classes in schools makes it important to observe student behaviors in class.

In the study, it was aimed to examine whether participation in the competition is effective on the sportsmanship (fair play) behaviors exhibited by the students in the PES class. For this purpose, the sportsmanship behaviors of the students were examined according to their participation in the competition in the PES class.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Model of the Research

The survey model, which is one of the quantitative research types, formed the model of the research. Survey studies are studies that aim to describe the views of large masses (Büyüköztürk et al., 2013).

This model was preferred because this research aimed to examine the effects of students' participation in competitions on the sportsmanship behaviors shown in the Physical Education and Sports class.

Subject group

The subjects consisted of 92 girls and 82 boys, 67 students at the 5th grade level, 38 students at the 6th grade level, 36 students at the 7th grade level, and 33 students at the 8th grade level, among the students of Istanbul Tuzla Piri Reis Secondary School in the 2021-2022 academic year. It consists of 174 children in total.

In the study, PECSBS was applied to volunteer students between the ages of 10-15 who competed and did not compete. Of the 174 students who participated in the study, 86 participated in the competition and 88 were students who never participated in the competition.

Data Collection

In the study, the Physical Education Class Sportsmanship Behavior Scale (PECSBS) developed by Koç (2013) was used in order to determine the sportsmanship behaviors of the students in the Physical Education class. The scale consists of a five-point Likert type. The scale separated positive behaviors (items 1, 2, 4, 7, 9, 11, 12, 14, 16, 19, 21) from negative behaviors (items 3, 5, 6, 8, 10, 13, 15, 17, 18, 20, 22). The reliability coefficient of the developed scale was determined by Koç (2013) as 0.88 for factor 1 and 0.86 for factor 2. When the reliability coefficient factor results are examined, it is determined that the scale used in the research is highly reliable.

Analysis of Data

SPSS program was used in the analysis and evaluation process of the data.

RESULTS

Table 1. Analysis of Physical Education and Sports Lesson Sportsmanship Behaviors of Secondary School Children Responding to the Scale by Gender

	Sex	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z	p
Exhibiting positive behavior total(epb)	Female	92	94,49	8693,50	-1,944	,052
	Male	82	79,65	6531,50		
Avoiding negative behavior total(anb)	Female	92	93,50	8602,00	-1,672	,095
	Male	82	80,77	6623,00		
Grand total	Female	92	96,90	8914,50	-2,609	,009
	Male	82	76,96	6310,50		

In Table 1, the physical education lesson sportsmanship behaviors of the secondary school children who answered the scale were analyzed according to their gender status. When the table is examined, the results of the physical education lesson sportsmanship scale of boys and girls showed that the rate of girls' displaying sportsmanship behavior in the Physical Education lesson was higher than that of boys.

Table 2. Analysis of Physical Education and Sports Lesson Sportsmanship Behaviors of Secondary School Children Who Answered the Scale According to Their Participation in Competition

	Did you join the competition?	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z	p
Exhibiting positive behavior total(epb)	Yes	86	90,48	7781,50	-,774	,439
	No	88	84,59	7443,50		
	Total	174				
Avoiding negative behavior total(anb)	Yes	86	89,82	7724,50	-,603	,546
	No	88	85,23	7500,50		
	Total	174				
Grand total	Yes	86	91,15	7839,00	-,946	,344
	No	88	83,93	7386,00		
	Total	174				

In Table 2, the physical education lesson sportsmanship status of the secondary school children who answered the scale was analyzed according to their participation in the competition. According to Table 2, there was no significant difference in sportsmanship behavior in the Physical Education lesson between the students who participated in the competition and those who did not.

Table 3. Analysis of Physical Education and Sports Lesson Sportsmanship Behaviors of Secondary School Children Responding to the Scale According to Grade Levels

	Class	N	Mean Rank	X ²	p	The group from which the difference originates
Exhibiting positive behavior total (epb)	5	67	95,51	6,877	,076	
	6	38	90,29			
	7	36	68,68			
	8	33	88,56			
Avoiding negative behavior total (anb)	5	67	96,59	5,711	,127	
	6	38	89,80			
	7	36	72,81			
	8	33	82,42			
Grand total	5	67	97,38	10,062	,018	5>7 p=0,013
	6	38	93,03			
	7	36	65,39			
	8	33	85,20			

In Table 3, the physical education course sportsmanship status of the secondary school children who answered the scale were analyzed according to their grade levels. 5 and 7 according to Table 3. There was a significant difference in sportsmanship behavior in Physical Education lesson between grades.

Table 4. Analysis of Physical Education and Sports Lesson Sportsmanship Behaviors of Secondary School Children Responding to the Scale by Participation Branch

	Branch	N	Mean Rank	X ²	p
Exhibiting positive behavior total(epb)	Team sports	51	46,60	4,283	,117
	Individual sports	17	45,62		
	Intelligence games	18	32,72		
	Total	86			
Avoiding negative behavior total(anb)	Team sports	51	43,39	,033	,984
	Individual sports	17	44,41		
	Intelligence games	18	42,94		
	Total	86			
Grand total	Team sports	51	46,41	3,783	,151
	Individual sports	17	45,50		
	Intelligence games	18	33,36		
	Total	86			

In Table 4, the physical education course sportsmanship status of the secondary school children who answered the scale were analyzed according to the branch of participation in the competition. According to Table 4, there was no significant difference in sportsmanship behavior in Physical Education lesson according to the branch of participation in the competition.

DISCUSSION

In this study, Physical Education and Sports lesson sportsmanship behaviors of secondary school children were evaluated in terms of gender, competition participation status, class level and competition

participation branches. Significant differences were found in the Physical Education and Sports lesson sportsmanship behaviors of the students according to gender ($p < 0.05$).

It has been found that the sportsmanship behavior exhibited by girls in Physical Education and Sports class is significantly higher than that of boys. In some studies, it has been shown that girls at the secondary school level have higher sportsmanship behaviors compared to boys (Gümüş and friends, 2016.).

It is believed that society's perspectives and expectations towards women have an impact on a higher rate of sporting behavior in girls. There was no statistically significant difference found in the participation of children in the competition. When the sportsmanship behaviors of children according to class levels are examined 5. and 7. It has been found that there is a statistically significant difference between the classes.

In a study conducted by Koç (2013) at the development stage of the scale, it was found that the sportsmanship rate of secondary school children decreases as the grade level increases. When the results of other studies were examined, a decrease in sportsmanship behaviors was observed as the class level and age increased (Esentürk, İlhan and Çelik 2015; Hacıcaferoğlu and friends, 2015; Aries, 2013; Koç and Tamer, 2016; Shields and friends, 2007; Türkmen and Varol, 2015).

Having the lowest grades in the 7th grade at the grade level shows that students may exhibit more aggressive behaviors in adolescence. At the same time, the onset of test anxiety can be shown as a factor in the decrease in sportsmanship behavior.

The fact that there is no significant difference between the branches of participation in the competition, but the team sports received the highest score, has created the idea that doing something with a group affects sportsmanship behavior Decently (Karafil A..the other. 2017).

In his study, he came to the idea that children participating in sports competitions positively increase the culture of cooperation and sense of solidarity, compliance with the rules required by sports, sharing, being tolerant, helping each other and human values. It has been found that female students act more in harmony with each other within the rules of sportsmanship compared to men with their friends. While students are more tolerant and tolerant of mistakes made in the game against each other at a young age, it is believed that they tend to exhibit more aggressive behavior in later life due to the tension and pressure caused by adolescence and exam anxiety.

CONCLUSION

As a result, in our study, there was no statistically significant difference between the students participating in the competition and the students not participating ($P > 0.05$). But when looked at according to the gender variable, there was a statistical difference between girls and boys in terms of total BEDSDÖ scores in the direction of an increase in girls ($P < 0.05$). It was determined that there was a difference in the comparisons made on the basis of class, and the group where this difference originated was between the 5th and 7th grades ($5 > 7$, $P < 0.05$).

In light of these results, the increase in sportsmanship of secondary school students reveals their personal thoughts, which are the sum of their participation in the competition, their education throughout their lives, family education and communication, and demographic appearance. The results of our study show that the fact that girls have a thin, gentle and more fragile structure in terms of their place in society, both in terms of their upbringing in the family and from the point of view of education and social life, may cause their sportsmanship dimensions to be better than that of boys. In this context, it may be necessary to give education to girls and boys with a different approach while providing sportsmanship education in BES lessons.

Author Contributions

Plan, design: SC,BY; **Material, methods and data collection:** BY; **Data analysis and comments:** SC; **Writing and corrections:** BY.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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KAYNAKLAR

- Büyüköztürk, Ş., Çakmak, E. K., Akgün, Ö. E., Karadeniz, Ş., & Demirel, F. (2013). Bilimsel Araştırma Yöntemleri. Ankara: Pegem Akademi. s. 177.
- Colak S., Başaran Z., Colak T., Aksu E., (2016) "The investigation of sports managers self efficacy levels of sportsmen management and sports clubs", TOJET: The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology, cilt.12.
- Doğar, Y., Yağmur, M. (2019). Beden eğitimi ve spor dersinin ortaokul öğrencileri üzerinde sportmenlik davranışı etkisinin incelenmesi (Kahramanmaraş İli Örneği). Journal of History School, 43, 1651-1665. Pehlivan, Z. (2004). Fair-play kavramının geliştirilmesinde okul sporunun yeri ve önemi. SPORMETRE Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi, II (2) 49-53.
- Esentürk OK, İlhan EL, Çelik OB (2015). Examination Of High School Students' Sportsmanlike Conducts In Physical Education Lessons According To Some Variability. Science, Movement and Health, 15 (2, Supplement): 627-634.
- Ford, D. W., Jubenville, C. B., & Phillips, M. B. (2012). The effect of the star sportsmanship education module on parents' self perceived sportsmans hip behaviors in youth sport. Journal of Sport Administration and Supervision, 4(1), 1-4.
- Hacıcaferoğlu, S., Selçuk, M. H., Hacıcaferoğlu, B., & Karataş, Ö. (2015). Ortaokullarda işlenen beden eğitimi ve spor derslerinin, sportmenlik davranışlarına katkısının bazı değişkenler açısından incelenmesi. International Journal of Science Culture And Sport (Intjcs), 3(4), 557-566.
- Karafil, A., Y., Atay, E., Ulaş, M., ve Melek, C. (2017). Spora katılımın beden eğitimi dersi sportmenlik davranışları üzerine etkisinin araştırılması. CBÜ Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi, 12(2), 1-11
- Koç, Y. & Tamer, K. (2016). A study on the sportsmanship behaviors of female students in physical education course according to different variables. Nigde University Journal of Physical Education and Sport Sciences, 7(1), 16-27.
- Koç, Y. (2013). Beden eğitimi dersi sportmenlik davranış ölçeği geçerlilik ve güvenilirlik çalışması. Erzincan Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi, 15(1):96-114.
- Shields D, La Voi N, Bredemeier B, Power F (2007): Predictors of poor sportpersonship in youth sports: personal attitudes and social influences. Journal of Sport & Exercise Psychology. 29(6), 747-762.
- Sivri İ., Örs A., İnaltekin A., Çolak T., Özbek A., Çolak E., Son M., (2017) "Kocaeli süper amatör futbol liginde farklı sıralarda yer alan iki takımın sporcularının maç öncesi kaygı düzeylerinin karşılaştırılması", Uluslararası 9. Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Öğretmenliği Kongresi, 19 - 22 Ekim 2017.
- Türkmen, M., Varol, S. (2015). Beden Eğitimi ve Spor dersinin ortaokul öğrencileri üzerinde sportmenlik davranışı oluşturma etkisinin belirlenmesi: (Bartın İl Örneği). Uluslararası Güncel Eğitim Araştırmaları Dergisi, 1(1), 42- 64
- Yapan, H. T. (2007). Spor Ahlakı. Gaziantep: Merkez Ofset. 7